

Whole-genome sequence of a *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* strain BLB250 isolated from the rhizosphere soil of an olive tree in Tunisia and exhibiting insecticidal activity

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Abstract

This study reports the whole-genome shotgun sequencing (WGS) of a *Bacillus thuringiensis* strain BLB250 isolated from olive tree rhizosphere soils in Tunisia and having a promising insecticidal activity. Previous analyses of this strain, by plasmid and profiling analogy with the reference strain HD133, revealed its assignment as an *aizawai* subspecies. It produces bipyramidal and cubical crystals, which is in accordance with its content of *cry1* and *cry2* genes, revealed by PCR amplification. The membership of BLB250 in the *Bacillus cereus* group, and more specifically the *B. thuringiensis* genus, was determined by combining the genomic analysis (using ANI and MLST classification) and the conventional taxonomy. The total size of the genome is 6.37 Mb, assembled into 231 contigs, with a contig N50 of 73.67 kb. Its genomic GC content was determined to be 34.72%. These data will provide a useful resource for future studies on the biocontrol mechanism of this promising *B. thuringiensis* strain to be used for agricultural pest management.

Introduction

Current pest control strategies consider the negative side effects from the accumulation of chemical pesticides in the environment. Consequently, eco-friendly alternatives are increasingly being sought after for pest control methods (Bravo *et al.*, 2011). The use of microbial pesticides, especially based on bacteria from the *Bacillus* genus, began to be remarkable (Liu *et al.*, 2026). The biopesticide formulations based on the bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) account for nearly 75 % of the total biopesticide market (Sujayanand *et al.*, 2021). *Bt*-based biopesticides have been successfully applied against several phytopathogenic insects in a specific manner with no toxicity against humans or other organisms, but with a variability in efficiency (Crickmore, 2000; Melo *et al.*, 2016). This entomopathogenic ability is based on the production of insecticidal crystalline proteins during the stationary and sporulation phases of its growth cycle, such as Cry and Cyt toxins, as well as the secretion of proteins during the vegetative growth, such as Vip (Andrés-Garrido *et al.*, 2020) and Sip toxins (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). Even though the insecticidal potential of *Bt* is the most studied, other virulence aspects have been broadly reported. In fact, *Bt* produces a variety of virulence factors responsible for antibacterial or antifungal effects. Indeed, *Bt* exhibits several hydrolytic enzymes *viz.*, chitinases, proteases, and beta-glucanases (Hyakumachi *et al.*, 2013; Hatice *et al.*, 2016), lipopeptides (Abderrahmani *et al.*, 2011), and bacteriocins (Kamoun *et al.*, 2011). In our previous work, the BLB250 strain was shown to be an HD133-like strain of *B. thuringiensis* with dual efficiency to the two Lepidopteran pests: *Spodoptera littoralis* (Noctuidae) and *Ephestia kuehniella* (Pyralidae), with promising LC₅₀ values of 56.2 mg g⁻¹ and 167.6 mg g⁻¹, respectively (BenFarhat-Touzri *et al.*, 2016). Preliminary studies have provided some answers regarding its superior efficacy compared to the reference strain. Nevertheless, we believe that the in-depth study provided by its WGS will be a reliable approach to shed light on the molecular and operational mechanisms underlying its

effectiveness in biocontrol, as well as its mechanism of biological control of insect pests.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

The *B. thuringiensis* strain BLB250 belongs to the bacterial collection of the Laboratory of Biopesticides at the Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax (Tunisia). It is isolated from the rhizosphere soil of an olive tree collected in Tunisia due to its efficiency against two Lepidopteran pests (*S. littoralis* and *E. kuehniella*). It is a sporulating *Bacillus* strain that produces bipyramidal and cubical crystals, which is in accordance with its content of *cry1* and *cry2* genes, revealed by PCR amplification. The assignment of strain BLB250 to the subspecies *aizawai* was done by plasmid profiling analogy with the *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* reference strain HD133 (BenFarhat-Touzri *et al.*, 2016). The strain was grown at 30 °C using LB medium (Driss *et al.*, 2005).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

The genomic DNA sequence from this isolate was acquired by MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK; <https://microbesng.com>), a sequencing service provider. The genomic DNA library was prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). The library was sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencer (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Adapters were trimmed from reads using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. *De novo* assembly was performed using SPAdes version 3.7

(Bankevich *et al.*, 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Taxonomic nomenclature

The Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) calculator (Yoon *et al.*, 2017) was used to classify and identify the BLB250 strain through the calculation of the OrthoANIu percentage with the *Bacillus thuringiensis* serovar *berliner* ATCC 10792 (*Bacillus thuringiensis* reference genome: ASM16161v1; RefSeq: GCF_000161615.1), a member of the *Bacillus cereus* group. Furthermore, the taxonomic nomenclature was confirmed using the PubMLST.org website (Jolley *et al.*, 2018).

Results

Data availability

The whole-genome shotgun for the BLB250 strain has been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under accession number JBYFAR000000000. The version described in this paper is JBYFAR010000000. Raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under the BioProject number PRJNA1465096 and SRA accession number SRR38517137.

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features for the BLB250 strain is listed in Table 1. The mean coverage is $63.49 \times$. The assembly of sequence reads resulted in 231 contigs, with the largest contig of 453441 bp. The cumulative contig lengths of the genome assembly yielded a genome size of 6.37 Mb, with a contig N50 of 73.67 kb. The strain had a GC content of 34.72%, 6559 protein-coding genes, 107 tRNAs, 1 tmRNA and 20 rRNAs.

Taxonomic classification

The taxon identification of strain BLB250 was first carried out using the ANI identification. An ANI value of 96.09% allowed its classification as a *B. thuringiensis* strain. However, using the MLST taxonomic nomenclature, a 100% sequence identity of core genes was found with *Bacillus cereus* (Table 2). Besides, the matching profile given by the Ribosomal MLST test showed the membership of the BLB250 to the species *cereus* (Table 3). Faced with this doubt raised for the assignment of BLB250, we resorted to the combination of the molecular and the conventional taxonomy (Carroll *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, BLB250 is a *Bacillus cereus sensu lato* strain that produces crystals (a unique and specific characteristic of *B. thuringiensis* strains) (BenFarhat-Touzri *et al.*, 2016), which allows its classification as a *Bacillus* biovar *Thuringiensis*.

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared before formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We encourage and welcome feedback from the community. Please get in touch with Dr. Fatma Driss (fatma.driss@gmail.com) for more information.

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Table 1: Summary statistics of the *B. thuringiensis* BLB250 strain isolated from olive tree rhizosphere soil collected in Tunisia.

Strain	Number of reads	Contigs (≥ 1 kb)	Largest contig (bp)	Total length (bp)	GC (%)	Mean coverage	N50 (bp)	CDS	tRNA	tm RNA	rRNA	Bioproject	Biosample	GenBank accession (reads)	GenBank accession (assembly)
BLB250	837323	197	453441	6375794	34.72	63.49	73678	6559	107	1	20	PRJNA1465096	SAMN59733855	SRR38517137	JBYFAR000000000

Table 2: Predicted taxa of BLB250.

Strain	Rank	Taxon	Support	Taxonomy
BLB250	SPECIES	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota > Bacilli > Bacillales > Bacillaceae > Bacillus > Bacillus cereus</i>

Table 3: Ribosomal MLST (Matching profile) taxonomic nomenclature of BLB250.

Strain	BLB250
rST	17318
Genus	<i>Bacillus</i>
Species	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>